

DIGITAL TWINNING FRAMEWORK FOR ELECTRIC DRIVE DESIGN

EM-TECH

Accelerated vehicle performance and efficiency evaluation

Flexible integration of a high-fidelity vehicle simulator and surrogate models

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTION:

Vehicle simulation tools play an important role in the design of next-generation electric vehicles for both OEMs, component developers, and researchers, as they allow rapid assessment of the impact of new technologies and systems on vehicle performance and efficiency while also helping to refine design choices of vehicle subsystems. However, the trade-off between component model accuracy and simplicity is a key factor. Striking the balance between accuracy and simplicity is essential both to understand correctly the impact of innovations at the vehicle level and to optimise system parameters, such as the control gains of vehicle control systems, which may require numerous simulation runs. To explore and assess the benefits of the EM-TECH solutions for different vehicle segments and operating conditions, an AVL_VSM/Simulink simulation toolchain has been adopted, where the high-fidelity vehicle simulator AVL_VSM is integrated with computationally efficient surrogate models of EM-TECH subsystems (e.g., those of the EM-TECH electric motors) as well as advanced control strategies proposed within the project.

This simulation environment is flexible; for example, it can be configured for electric vehicles with different powertrain layouts, such as onboard or in-wheel motor solutions. Within the project, it has been used to evaluate improvements in vehicle performance and efficiency across a wide range of vehicle types (onboard/in-wheel) and segments, driving scenarios, and operating conditions enabled by the EM-TECH innovations in conjunction with novel EM-TECH control solutions (e.g., model predictive ABS controllers, shifting strategies for the e-gear, and AI based traction control strategies).

Figure 1: Two-stage helical gear transmission developed by AVL

IMPACT & NEXT STEPS:

Use of the developed simulation environment for testing control methods for BEVs in future research projects.

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